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Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis of Land Suitability for the Construction of open Refugee Accommodation Facilities in Greece

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ABSTRACT

Over the last five years, Greece has been one of the main gateways of refugees and migrants in the EU. In order to deal with that migration and refugee crisis, the Greek Government constructed several Refugee Accommodation Facilities and Reception and Identification Centers. Due to their temporary and emergent nature, these facilities were constructed without following strict planning procedures and regulations. This study aims to provide a methodological multi-criteria framework based on a narrative literature review and the use of spatial analysis in order to inform spatial planning policies for allocating refugee facilities. The results of the literature review revealed six research articles, one study and two textbooks. They led to the listing of twenty-three (23) spatial criteria of social, infrastructure and geographic components. For the creation of the spatial suitability maps, all twenty-three criteria were included in the multi-criteria decision algorithm concerning the spatial planning legislation of Greece. The results of the performed analysis showed that the 6,267.65 km² of the Greek territory are suitable for the construction of such a facility, while the 125,761.34 km² are not. Also, our study highlighted the fact that only 9 out of the 36 current Accommodation Facilities and Reception and Identification Centers have been constructed within or close (250 meters) to suitable areas. Such results indicate a lack of planning, which may have multiple effects on the population (native and foreign). Additionally, the results signify the vital contribution of Geographical Information Systems (GIS) in assessing land suitability for the spatial planning of refugee accommodation. The proposed criteria and methodology can be a valuable planning tool for migration policy and decision-makers internationally.

Keywords: Geographic Information Systems, Refugee Camps, Spatial Analysis, Multicriteria Decision Analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

During the last five years, the escalating conflict resulted by the “Arab Spring” in the wider geographical region of the Middle East and North Africa has been the main reason behind the increasing displacement of millions of people. Besides, the multi-year civil war in Syria speeded up the above phenomenon. (Triandafyllidou, 2014; Mavrommatis, 2016).

Many asylum seekers and migrants started crossing the Mediterranean (Aegean islands, Lampedusa, Linosa, Malta, and in some cases, the Canary Islands) (Rapoport & Moraga, 2014), in their attempt to find asylum in an EU country and continue their movement through other European countries, such as the Republic of Northern Macedonia, Serbia, Croatia, Slovenia, Hungary, and Austria, and eventually to end up in a high-income country, such as Germany or Sweden. The increasing concern of this human mobility of migrants and refugees prompted the EU in 2015 to apply several budgetary and operational measures (e.g. refugee camps) (European

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Commission, 23 Sep 15 & 4 May 16)

Under the Schengen Regulation, Greece was obliged in 2016 to construct Refugee Accommodation Facilities, namely Refugee Camps (RC), and Reception and Identification Centers (RIC) in order to protect its international borders efficiently and sustainably (European Commission, 2 Feb 16). In order to meet that obligation, the Greek Government established the Law 4368/2016, under which the Armed Forces should build and, in some cases, operate the RIC and RC. In January 2020, Greece had 30 RC and 6 RIC, having recorded 1,202,518 refugees and migrants since 2014 [2]. However, only 115,600 of them still live in the country, with 74,400 living on the islands and 41,200 in the mainland (UNHCR, fact sheet 1-31 Jan 2020). The majority of them (81,14%) still live in Refugee Camps (RC) or Reception and Identification Centers (RIC) and only 21,793 of them have been accommodated in homes provided by the ESTIA/UNHCR program (UNHCR, ESTIA Accommodation Capacity Weekly Update as of 17 Mar 2020).

Still, in February of 2020, the Greek government were planning to build three new RC at three Aegean Islands (Lesvos, Samos, Kos) [1]. However, the people who live in these RCs and RICs have multiple biological, learning, social and professional needs, that are usually unmet. To address and mitigate such needs, we aimed to propose a Land suitability analysis (Spatial Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis or SMCDA) as multi-criteria methodological framework, for land suitability evaluation and spatial planning of refugee accommodation facilities in the country.

2 METHODS

We considered the international literature to identify both the applicable criteria and proposed analysis. The most recent search was executed in April 2019. As the researchers found, concerned different countries, and in order to classify and calibrate the criteria as accurately and objectively as possible, we consolidated the Greek planning legislation. The appropriate spatial data were collected either from Greek governmental and Administrative sources or environmental and geological organisations of the European Union. The only level that was driven from an unofficial source (Open Street Maps) is the road network, which is considered valid and up to date. Even though the data came from different sources and have been generated at different periods, we assumed that reflect the current picture.

Table 1 displays the 23 criteria that were applied for the land suitability calculation, along with their division into separate classes. The criteria are depicted in five main categories: a) Physical Geography, b) Transportation Infrastructure, c) Security, d) Social Infrastructure and e) Society (Soltani, A. et al. 2014; Cetinkaya, C. et al., 2016; Handbook for Emergencies, 2015). A score was assigned to each of them, ranging from “0” (lowest suitability) to “10” (highest suitability). Also, we excluded from the geoprocessing analysis the areas that were entirely inappropriate for the host of such constructions to avoid receiving any value from any other criterion.

Table 1. Suitability Criteria

Category	Criteria	Classification	Points	Source/Scale
Physical Geography scale=1: 250.000	Slope	0%-1%	0	European Environment Agency/cell size 25m
		1%-2%	8	
		2%-4%	10	
		4%-5%	7	
		5%-max	Exclusion	
	Distance from lakes and rivers	0-200m	Exclusion	Hellenic Government via http://geodata.gov.gr
		200m-max	10	

	Distance from active faults	0-200m	Exclusion	The European Database of Seismogenic Faults (EDSF)/ scale= 1: 250.000
		200m-max	10	
	Avoiding from landslides	Category of probable landslide 1-3	10	European soil data centre/ cell size: 200m
		Category of probable landslide 4	5	
		Category of probable landslide 5	Exclusion	
	Distance from Natura 2000 areas	Inside the area	Exclusion	Hellenic Government via http://geodata.gov.gr/ scale=1: 5.000
		Outside the Natura area	10	
	Avoiding areas with extreme climate conditions	Areas with polar/ cold climate	Exclusion	European soil data centre European scale, very general
		Areas over 800m altitude	Exclusion	
		Areas with cold climate and warm summer	5	
		Any other area	10	
	Areas with water-permeable soils	No water-permeable land	0	European soil data centre/ cell size 1000m
		Water-permeable land	10	
	Transportation	Proximity to roads	0-1klm	10
1-3klm			8	
3-5klm			6	
5-20klm			4	
20-50klm			2	
50klm-max			0	
Proximity to railroads		0-1klm	10	Hellenic Government via http://geodata.gov.gr scale=1: 250.000
		1-5klm	9	
		5-10klm	8	
		10-20klm	5	
		20-50klm	3	
		50-80klm	2	
		80klm - max	0	
Proximity to airports		0-1klm	10	European Environment Agency /scale=1:100.000
		1-5klm	9	
		5-10klm	8	
		10-20klm	5	
		20-50klm	3	
		50-80klm	2	
		80klm - max	0	
Proximity to ports		0-1klm	10	
		1-5klm	9	
		5-10klm	8	
		10-20klm	5	
		20-50klm	3	
		50-80klm	2	
	80klm - max	0		

Social Infrastructure	Proximity to hospitals and primary care health centres	0-1klm	10	Information society SA. Public Buildings via http://geodata.gov.gr Posts/scale=1: 250.000
		1-5klm	8	
		5-10klm	6	
		10-20klm	4	
		20-50klm	2	
		50klm-max	0	
	Proximity to firefight stations	0-1klm	10	
		1-5klm	8	
		5-10klm	6	
		10-20klm	4	
		20-50klm	2	
		50klm-max	0	
	Proximity to primary, middle and high schools	0-1klm	10	
		1-5klm	8	
		5-10klm	6	
		10-20klm	4	
		20-50klm	2	
		50klm-max	0	
Security	Distance from a high voltage electricity network	0-200m	Exclusion	Independent Electricity Transmission Operator / scale=1: 250.000
		200m-max	10	
	Distance from waste disposal areas	0-500m	Exclusion	European Environment Agency/scale=1:100.000
		500m-2klm	0	
		2klm-μέγιστο	10	
	Distance from quarry areas	0-1klm	Exclusion	
		1klm-max	10	
	Distance from industrial areas	0-1klm	Exclusion	
		1klm-max	10	
	Distance from International borders	0-50klm	0	Hellenic Government via http://geodata.gov.gr/ scale=1: 50.000
		50klm-max	10	
	Society	Proximity to settlements with a population between 1.000-30.000 people	0-1klm	10
1-5klm			8	
5-10klm			6	
10-20klm			4	
20-50klm			2	
50klm-max			0	
Distance from settlements with a population between 1-999 people and more than 30.001 people		0-2klm	0	
		2klm-max	10	
Distance from a high touristic value attractiveness		Areas of high economic value from touristic activities	0	Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy/ scale=1: 250,000.
		Areas of medium economic value from touristic activities	8	
		Areas of low economic value from touristic activities	10	
Distance from archaeological sites		0-1klm	0	Pleiades, Ancient World Mapping Center, the Stoa Consortium /scale=1: 250,000.
		1-3klm	5	
		3klm-max	10	

In the category of Physical Geography, we analysed seven distinct criteria. Specifically, for the classification of the criteria “Distance from rivers and lakes”, “Distance from active faults” and “Distance from Natura 2000 areas” we considered the Greek spatial planning legislation and the scale of the input layers. Moreover, the “levels of spatial probability of generic landslide occurrence” and the classification of the Climate-Physiographic Regions informed the criteria “Avoiding landslides” and “Avoiding areas with extreme climate conditions” (ELSUS V2: Wilde, M. et al. 2018; Günther, A., et al. 2014). Regarding the criterion “Areas with water-permeable soils (WPS)”, we applied a prototype algorithm (1). In order to identify the appropriate areas with water-permeable soils, we combined the preferable values of three separate raster layers of soil hydraulic properties of Europe with the “Raster Calculator Tool”. These soil indicators were a) Field capacity after rain (FC values from 0,57475 to 0,19885), b) Saturated water content (SWC values from 0,365293 to 0,628222) and c) Saturated hydraulic conductivity (SHC values from -1,55507 to 1,79775). We identified the appropriate areas with moderate permittable soils applying the following prototype algorithm:

$$\text{WPS} = (\text{FC} < 0.4) \ \& \ (\text{SWC} > 0.4) \ \& \ (\text{SHC} > 1) \quad (1)$$

In order to classify all the criteria of the “transportation infrastructure” category, we studied the network density of each transportation mean. For example, roads had a higher density than the railways or the number of ports and airports. Thus, we divided the distance from roads in much smaller classes than the other three transportation means.

Consequently, after examination of the distance density for the three “social Infrastructure” criteria (number the hospitals/primary care health centres, the firefight stations and the primary/middle/high schools) we divided the categories into similar classes. Likewise, for the appropriate distances for majority of the criteria (high voltage electricity network, waste disposal areas, quarry areas, industrial areas) of the “security” category we considered the Greek spatial planning legislation and the scale of the input layers.

Finally, for the last category “society” we used four criteria. We divided the criterion “Proximity to the local population” into two new distinct criteria that were not existed in the literature, as following: “proximity to medium urban populations” ($1,000 \leq \text{pop} \leq 30,000$), and (b) “distance from minimal (0-999 inhabitants) and substantial urban concentrations ($>30,000$ inhabitants)”. The purpose of this split was initially to avoid minimal urban areas as they would be inadequate to provide the infrastructure and services which the host population may need. Secondly, the avoidance of substantial urban concentrations was to avoid increased population densities within already densely populated areas. Following that distinction, the areas to be avoided received a lower score (0).

Besides, for the criterion “distance from high touristic value attractiveness,” we applied the classification of the National Framework of Spatial Planning & Sustainable Development for tourism. Our classification was informed by the above policy, which divides the Greek territory into three main categories, according to the impact of the touristic activities in the local economy. Hence, we designed the separate classes, respectively, in order to avoid the sitting of an RC or RIC in areas where the touristic activities are essential for the economic activity of the region. Regarding the criterion “distance from archaeological sites,” we decided a priori that the smallest class should be at least 1km away from any archaeological site because the Greek spatial planning legislation specialises differently to each archaeological site.

All the above criteria formed 23 separate raster layers using the “Euclidean Distance Tool” “Select By Attributes Tool” and the “Slope Tool”, which helped to form the distances from several criteria and the new processed layers (Supplementary Figures 1, 2). Then with the use of the “Reclassify Tool” and the “Set Null Tool” the above-processed layers were classified appropriately according to the classes of Table 1 (Supplementary Figures 3, 4). Finally, the 23 new raster layers were added with the “Raster Calculator Tool”. Thus, each potentially appropriate cell received a value due to this prosthetic overlap, assuming that all criteria were equally weighted. As a

result, the highest value that a raster cell could get was “230” (23 criteria for a maximum value of “10”) and was considered as the most appropriate location for the construction of a refugee camp. In contrast, the least appropriate were those cells that could get the lowest possible value “71”. Finally, we constructed a categorical variable of 6 categories according to the results of suitability (Natural Breaks). It is worth noticing that the difference in the reference scale (most commonly 1:250,000) of the input layers and cell size, led us to choose the to the creation of all of these geoprocessing raster layers with a spatial resolution of 250m cell size to avoid any possible scale accuracy errors. Figure 1 summarises the flow chart of the methodology used.

Figure 1: Scheme of land suitability calculation.

3 RESULTS

The results of the land suitability assessment are shown in Figure 2. The map indicated that no cell/area approached the maximum or minimum scores on all 23 factors, as the values range from “134-222”. The map depicts the land suitability in the whole Greek territory in six categories (Natural Breaks) as following: Excellent (grade 193 - 222), Very Good (grade 182 - 192), Good (grade 173 - 182), Fair (grad. 163 - 172), Poor (grad. 134 - 162) suitability and Excluded areas. The accompanying maps show the two largest areas with “excellent” suitability.

Notably, most of the country is considered unsuitable (125,761.34 km²), followed by “Fair” (2,307.8 km²), followed by “Very Good” (1,155.12 km²), followed by the category “Poor” (1,108 km²), then the category “Good” (964,217 acres) and finally the category “Excellent” (733,115 acres). Also, within Ilia’s Regional Unit (RU) (392,875 acres), there is located the largest area of “Excellent” suitability. That was followed by the Messenia’s RU with 186,125 acres and the Magnesia’s RU with 165,125 acres.

Surprisingly, considering the scale of work and data analysis, only the 9 out of the 36 existing Refugee Camps (RC) and Reception and Intensification Centers (RIC) are currently located within the margins of the proposed suitable areas. This result also includes areas that are within 250m from “suitable areas” in order to avoid and spatial bias of scale. According to our analyses, the existing RC that was appropriately located are: a) the RC in Kato Milia Pieria, b) the RC in Nea Kavala Polykastro; c) the RIC in Fylakio Evros; d) the RC in Myrsini Andravida; e) the RC in Ritsona, Evia; f) the RIC in Moria Lesbos; g) the RC in Lavrio Attica; h) the RC in Vial Chios, and i) the RC in Kypselochori Larissa.

The primary statistical parameters of land suitability for the Regional Units (Average, Standard Deviation, Minimum, Maximum, Suitable Area) shown that the of Piraeus’s RU has the highest average score (194.67) and 188 acres are suitable across it. The Evros’s RU has the most suitable land (1,161,625 acres) with an average value of 171.05 and a maximum value of 203. Only the Messenia’s RU has the highest value (222), with an average value of 189.18 and 544,438 suitable acres.

Figure 2. Land suitability for constructing an Open Refugee Accommodation Facility.

4 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we investigated the most suitable areas for the construction of an Open Refugee Accommodation Facility in Greece through GIS software and multi-criteria analysis of 23 factors. According to our analysis, the 125,761.34 km² of Greece are not suitable to host such a facility. A possible explanation of this result may be the contribution of the significant percentage of areas with high altitude (over 800m above the sea level) and the areas with a slope over 5% that were excluded. Another important finding is that 9 out of 36 existing RC and RIC have been constructed within inappropriate areas. A possible explanation for this result may be the lack of social and societal criteria for their construction. In this analysis, specific criteria that meet the survival needs of the host population, and also the learning and social ones were taken into vital consideration.

According to the existing evidence, the suitability of Refugee Accommodation Facilities has been measured with a different approach and methodology. They were mostly focusing on much smaller areas and not in the whole country's territory. Specifically the Cetinkaya's et al. (2016) extensive research, particularly detailed on the siting of Syrian Refugee Hosting Structures in southeastern Turkey used the fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (AHP) method to select and calibrate the appropriate areas, in combination with the TOPSIS method and the extensive use of GIS. The next study referred to the deployment of an emergency evacuation structure with displaced people due to war, (Pradhan, 2017), which focused on Al-Anbar province in Iraq use the fuzzy logic to determine the weights. Trivedi & Singh (2017) also focus their research on two areas of Nepal use the fuzzy AHP method. Studies by Sadidi et al. (2014), Şentürk, & Erener (2017) and Moğulkoç & Türk, (2018) were concerned with the location of earthquake victims in Iran and

Turkey using GIS. Specifically, Sadidi et al. (2014) used four different algorithms (AHP, OWA, Fuzzy Logic, TOPSIS) to calibrate 10 criteria, while Şentürk & Erener (2017) used the AHP and Moğulkoç & Türk (2018) use a simple weight addition to the five criteria they use.

The connotation of our findings is very crucial because it sheds light on the absence of Spatial Planning of the Greek Government, combined with insufficiencies in the Migration Policy (delays in recognition of refugee status). The RIC and RC were proposed to the Greek society as a temporary solution for hosting facilities. However, the reality showed that they still operate for the last three years, and none knows for how long they will continue to operate.

However, these results need to be interpreted with caution as there several limitations. It is vital to bear in mind that in our study, the small scale of the input layers did not allow a detailed examination and affected the level of interpretation of the results. Inevitably, this scale led to the selection of large geographical Regions for the analysis. Furthermore, methodologically the simple prosthetic overlap methodology was only preferred because of the significant study's extent. The selection to examine the land suitability of the whole country did not allow the proper weighting of the criteria. One of the main reasons for our preference not to weight the significance of each criterion is the geographic specificity of each Regional Unit (NUTS 3). Otherwise, any weight calculation in any criteria would impulsively and subjectively conclude to "favour" one area and "disfavour" another. With respect and sincere evaluation of the characteristics of each Regional Unit for more detailed studies need to be conducted in the future.

Under these circumstances, the establishment of a spatial policy that will meet the basic social inclusion needs is significant. They should also provide, respect for individual value and dignity, and an appropriate environment for skill development, freedom of expression and movement. Thus it essential for such facilities to provide proximity to health and education structures, connection to the urban fabric and the local population. With the use of GIS, multi-criteria spatial analysis and the proposed medium-term planning and methodology, any social dissatisfaction and several spatial issues can be resolved with better and faster management. Moreover, an increase in the policy-makers communication between them and the experts of Regional Planning is likely to lead to more sustainable refugee/migration policies. The results of the present work can be used as a starting point for the design and implementation of new, more detailed, larger-scale spatial analysis studies. They can be focusing on the extent of specific Regional Units or Municipalities, assessing the importance of the weighting criteria, respectively, their needs and their capabilities. These facilities are not proposed as a solution to the refugee problem as this should be considered under many social, economic, political and legal reforms, but they aim to support a part of its operational management and a national planning framework policy. Thus, in this study, we proposed as more appropriate a medium-term planning procedure, even for these "temporary" open hosting facilities.

Future studies should take into account the criteria that were not applied in this study, such as the size and ownership of the area, and the financial cost of operating the facility. Also, qualitative characteristics, such as the cultural characteristics of the refugees and attitudes of the local population, should be considered.

5 SOFTWARE

The software that we used for the generation of the raster layers of Euclidean Distance, Reclassify and the Geoprocessing outcomes of surface analysis such as "slope" was the ArcMap 10.7 (student/ personal license: 9222732977, Reference ID: 442603373769), with the key toolboxes used being "Analysis Tools", "Spatial Analyst" Tools and "Data Management Tools".

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